

***Lernaea* Infection (Anchor worm)**

Lernaea species, commonly known as "anchor worms", are crustacean, copepod parasites that can infect and cause disease and death in many types of freshwater fish, especially wild-caught and pond-raised species. *Lernaea* infections are more common during the summer months and are more common in stagnant or slow-moving bodies of water.

Common sites of *Lernaea* infection include the skin, fins, gills, and oral cavity (Figure 1). Large numbers of lernids in copepodid stages can kill small fish, damaging their gills and making it difficult for the fish to breathe. When the female parasites attach to the fish, they dig deep into the tissue and eventually insert an anterior anchor into the fish's body. Severe focal inflammation and bleeding may occur at the site of attachment, and the area may appear red and ulcerated.

To the naked eye, the most commonly observed life stage of the organism - the adult female - appears as small, thin "threads" or "hairs" about 25 mm long. Under the microscope, the long, tubular body has an anchor at the anterior end and paired egg sacs at the posterior end (Figure 2). The anchor, located in the anterior ("head") region, is usually embedded in the host's tissue, and the posterior end, with its egg sac, extends into the water column. Juvenile life stages, especially copepodid stages, can also be seen on skin, fin or gill samples using a microscope (Figure 5). A fish health professional should be consulted for an accurate diagnosis, as adult female *Lernaea* can be confused with plant fibers, fungi or other organisms. It is necessary to use a microscope to examine wet mounts of the affected areas (skin, gills, mouth cavity, fins) to confirm the presence of this parasite.

Anchor worm (fig 01)

Eggs of Anchor worms (fig 02)

Neguvon 13g for 16 tanks

Neguvon mixing to water

Anchor worm head part (fig 05)

Anchor worm infection in tilapia

Anchor worm infection, caused by the crustacean parasite *Lernaea cypriniacea*, is a common and serious problem for tilapia farmers.

Pathogens

- ❖ *Lernaea cypriniacea*, a copepod parasite with two distinct stages:
- ❖ Adult females: Appear as elongated, red worms attached to the fish's skin and muscles.
- ❖ Naupliar larvae: Free-swimming in the water column, infecting new fish.

Anchor worm head part

Egg sac of anchor worm

Symptoms of infection

- ❖ Visible anchor worms protruding from the skin, often near the fins or head.
- ❖ Soreness and inflammation around the attachment site.
- ❖ Flushing, scratching, or irregular swimming due to anger.
- ❖ Secondary infections due to damaged tissue.
- ❖ Growth retardation and weight gain.

Effects on Tilapia

- ❖ Anchor worms feed on blood and tissue, interfering with fish health and growth.
- ❖ Severe infections can lead to secondary bacterial infections, anemia and even death.
- ❖ Decreased sales of infected fish due to injuries and consumer concerns.

Management Strategies

- ❖ Maintaining good water quality and sanitation in ponds.
- ❖ Quarantine new fish before introducing them into established populations.
- ❖ Manual removal of adult worms by vortexing or forceps (effective for low-level infections).
- ❖ Topical treatment with chemicals such as pyrethroids, organophosphates, or hydrogen peroxide (requires caution and compliance with regulations).
- ❖ Neguvon treatment. (Trichlorfon 97%)
- ❖ Medicated food with anti-parasitic ives such as levamisole or emamectin benzoate (effective for large-scale infections).

Neguvon treatment for anchor worm infection

Article by: R.M.P.P Bandula

Undergraduate

Faculty of Technology

University of Colombo